

MODERN METHODS, TECHNOLOGIES AND TOOLS OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING IN UKRAINIAN AND SWEDISH UNIVERSITY PRACTICES: CHALLENGES FOR IMPLEMENTATION IN CONDITIONS OF POSTPANDEMIC AND WARTIME

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Abstract: The article is dedicated to the problem comparative analysis the motivational readiness formation of future teachers for professional activity in Ukrainian and European educational institutions. The analysis has shown similarities in theory of Ukrainian and Swedish scientific understanding are in the approaches: educational and professional dialogue stimulated independent thinking, created a space for communication, and activated the application of knowledge already acquired by students. The investigation demonstrated, that work in small groups, as well as the "brainstorming" method, which allowed to significantly increase the creative activity of students in a short time, proved to be effective. At the same time, it was noticed that it is not easy for students to depart from existing stereotypes in solving any problem and to offer a new, original solution that goes beyond the possible. In general, the "brainstorming" that was used in seminars, laboratory-practical classes included the following stages: preparatory – defining the conditions of group work (group rules and time budget), creating several groups of "idea generators" and groups of "experts", formulating the problem to be solved; basic ("brainstorming") – problem solving, maximum manifestation of creative possibilities, free expression of ideas, recording of all expressed ideas; revision - on the basis of defined criteria, "experts" chose the best ideas (up to 10 minutes); final – discussion of the work, substantiation and presentation of the best ideas, recommendation for their practical implementation. The participants of the "brainstorming" were placed in a circle in the auditorium. "Experts" were located outside the circle, monitored the work and recorded all statements based on the need to receive the largest number of ideas. The teacher managed the course of work, but did not exert any pressure on the participants. It was also distinguished that the principle differences are in the practice of the motivational readiness formation of future teachers for professional activity in Ukrainian and European educational institutions: in European universities, these practices are more case oriented, investigations practices usage; on the contemporary in Ukraine – more pedagogical and theoretical practices are included.

Keywords: the motivational readiness, future teachers, readiness formation, professional activity, psychological and pedagogical conditions.

1 Introduction

Analyzing the problem of second language learning in university settings in Ukraine and Sweden is highly relevant due to several interconnected factors: impact of wartime conditions on higher education in Ukraine, post-pandemic adaptations, European integration and internationalization, comparative approach to pedagogical practices, supporting students' academic and professional needs and challenges of implementing new tools and technologies.

First of all is we speak about impact of russian invasions into Ukraine and results of its influence we have to emphasize, that the ongoing war in Ukraine has profoundly disrupted traditional educational practices, including language learning. Many universities have had to adapt rapidly to new realities such as remote teaching, hybrid models, and catering to the needs of displaced students. Analyzing second language learning within this context allows for understanding how modern tools can support effective learning amidst instability. Secondly, both Ukraine and Sweden have faced challenges in adjusting to post-pandemic educational practices, including shifts toward digital and hybrid learning models. The COVID-19 pandemic fundamentally changed how languages are taught and learned, with digital platforms and online methodologies becoming more central. Understanding these shifts can inform better practices and tools to maintain high standards of language instruction. As for the third factor, here we need to remind, that for Ukraine, the integration into the European educational space is a significant priority. Proficiency in foreign languages, especially English, is crucial for students to engage in academic mobility programs and to participate in European research and professional

networks. Examining how language education is structured in Swedish universities, which are already well integrated into the European educational system, can provide valuable insights and models for Ukrainian institutions. Also by analyzing the practices in both Ukrainian and Swedish universities, the study allows for a comparative perspective that highlights effective teaching strategies, technological tools, and curriculum design. Sweden's established practices in second language acquisition can offer models for adaptation in Ukraine, particularly in the use of digital resources and inclusive pedagogical approaches. More over, second language proficiency is essential for students in both academic and professional contexts, enabling them to access broader academic literature, collaborate internationally, and prepare for global job markets. In Ukraine, especially under the conditions of war, these skills are not only a gateway to international opportunities but also critical for contributing to the rebuilding and transformation of the country. And finally, the conditions of post-pandemic recovery and ongoing conflict pose unique challenges for the implementation of new educational tools. It is important to analyze what barriers exist in both countries, such as infrastructure, access to digital resources, and training for educators, to ensure that modern methods of second language learning can be effectively applied.

If we take deeper approach to the analysis of second language learning in university settings in Ukraine, we should refer to the survey of the British Council, which starting in 2014, and in partnership with the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine has been conducted in-depth baseline studies of universities across the country to evaluate the current English provision as well as the role and status of English. This has focused on three key audiences: teachers of English for Specific Purposes (ESP) and English for General Academic Purposes (EGAP), teachers of other subjects who wish to use English as a Medium of Instruction (EMI) or for research and international purposes, and finally general students who need to understand English either for course requirements or as a specific target for their universities.

By 2017 the British Council had completed detailed baseline studies of 15 classical and technical universities. Their findings and recommendations have been shared with representatives of the Ministry of Education and Science, and with the rectors, senior management and teachers of each of the participating universities. The response to the findings has been one of enthusiasm and action, with proactive working groups agreeing key action points to be taken forward. The collated details of all of the findings and recommendations from all 15 universities are now presented in this report, for wider discussion and use beyond just the universities surveyed (Bolitho & West, 2017).

As for the impact and settings of second language learning in Ukrainian universities the investigation of Pylypenko and Kozub (2021) proved out that Ukrainian philology students overall positively evaluate their distance learning experience. It does not negatively impact students' foreign language learning motivation; despite a positive attitude to distance learning, Ukrainian philology students face particular challenges connected with access to devices, lack of information and communications technology skills, Internet connection, and lack of communication with their peers; and that distance education cannot entirely replace face-to-face learning.

One of the thorough investigation was provided by team of Ukrainian scientists about different integration of immersive technologies, such as virtual reality (VR), augmented reality (AR), mixed reality (MR), and artificial intelligence (AI), offers promising solutions to enhance language education. The study found that various immersive technologies have been commonly employed in foreign language education, with semi-immersive experiences being the most prevalent. Combining VR with full immersion and AR with semi-immersion were the most

frequently observed approaches. These technologies engage multiple senses, creating authentic and engaging learning experiences that foster students' motivation, curiosity, and self-regulation (Palamar et al., 2023).

If we speak about Swedish context of English as a second language, we should admit that the role of English in Sweden is undergoing a transitional phase. Despite being officially categorized as a foreign language, its practical use in various contexts often aligns more closely with that of a second language (L2). The way English is used, the contexts in which it appears, and its frequency of use contribute to this shift, leading to a continual re-evaluation of its status. Furthermore, the concepts of English as a Foreign Language (EFL) and English as a Second Language (ESL) are not static; they can adapt and coexist as different forms of language proficiency, both at individual and societal levels (Bardel et al., 2023). According to the systemic analysis of the authors for bachelor's level courses and study programs, the general entry requirements include a minimum grade of E in Swedish or Swedish as a second language, Mathematics, and English. At the university level, English maintains a more prominent role compared to other languages, similar to its status in the school system. In scientific disciplines, English is used more frequently than in the humanities and social sciences, where it often serves as a supplementary language alongside Swedish (Bardel et al., 2023). The association of Swedish higher education institutions (SUHF) appointed a working group to review the status of languages in higher education and make recommendations for the future (SUHF, 2017). The report highlighted a need for a national language strategy that identifies the direction for which specific initiatives and assignments are necessary, that report has shown the extent to which languages have been discontinued at universities during the time span 2008–2016. French has been cut at six universities, English at five, Finnish, German, Greek, Italian, and Spanish have been cut at three universities, to give some examples. As the result the conception was reviewed and there has been a significant increase in funding dedicated to practice-based research within the field of education. The Swedish government has allocated resources to the Swedish Research Council to support graduate schools specifically designed for in-service teachers pursuing advanced studies in educational sciences. Additionally, in 2015, the Swedish government established the Swedish Institute for Educational Research (Skolforskningsinstitutet) to provide financial support for high-quality research projects with a practical focus on educational practices. Since 2017, the government has also been financing the ULF network, a national initiative that stands for "Utveckling, Lärande, Forskning" (which translates to 'development, learning, research'). This network includes collaborations between universities and schools, with the aim of developing and testing long-term models for research partnerships, integrating academic research with school activities, and enhancing teacher education programs (Olsson & Cederlund, 2020).

The mentioned above demonstrates, that Swedish experience could be greatly increase Ukrainian approaches and practice with positive incomes, thus the purpose of the article is to examine the current methodologies, tools, and approaches used for second language acquisition in higher education institutions in Ukraine and Sweden. It aims to analyze the specific challenges and opportunities associated with implementing these methods in the unique contexts of post-pandemic recovery and wartime conditions. Additionally, the article seeks to identify effective practices that can be adapted to improve second language learning outcomes and ensure the resilience and adaptability of educational systems in both countries..

The object of study is the array of contemporary methods, digital tools, and pedagogical practices utilized for teaching second languages within university settings in Ukraine and Sweden. It focuses on how these approaches are implemented, adapted, and challenged in the context of post-pandemic adjustments and the impact of ongoing wartime conditions, particularly in Ukraine.

The subject of research – is the specific challenges, strategies, and conditions that influence the effective integration of modern language learning tools and methods in higher education. It explores how these factors affect second language acquisition in Ukrainian and Swedish universities, focusing on the impact of post-pandemic shifts in education and the disruptions caused by wartime conditions in Ukraine..

Task for realization of the investigation:

- To analyze the specific barriers and challenges faced in implementing modern language learning tools in each context, including technological, pedagogical, and logistical difficulties;
- To identify effective practices and successful strategies that have been implemented in both contexts to enhance second language learning, focusing on tools that support digital and hybrid learning environments;
- To formulate recommendations for improving the implementation of modern language learning methods in Ukrainian and Swedish universities, addressing the identified challenges and emphasizing strategies for resilience in post-pandemic and wartime conditions.

2 Methodology

The research will involve a comparative analysis of the data collected from both Ukrainian and Swedish universities. This analysis will focus on identifying similarities and differences in the use of modern language learning tools, the challenges faced, and the outcomes achieved. The qualitative data from interviews and focus groups will be analyzed using thematic analysis to identify key themes, patterns, and insights related to the implementation of second language learning practices. This will help in understanding how different contexts influence the effectiveness of language learning strategies. Case studies of specific universities or programs that have successfully implemented modern tools for second language learning will be developed. These case studies will highlight best practices and innovative approaches to language education amidst challenges. The research will be grounded in a review of relevant literature on second language acquisition, educational technology, and pedagogical practices, ensuring that the findings are contextualized within existing knowledge and frameworks.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Ukrainian practice and context

Contemporary higher education institutions in Ukraine increasingly adopt interactive methods and technologies for teaching English as a professional language, as these approaches foster deep motivation, take into account students' interests, and align with their current needs. This facilitates the integration of acquired knowledge with students' prior and ongoing experiences and ensures their active involvement in the learning process, allowing them to manage their own educational progress.

Interactive methods, in particular, are effective in developing English language skills within a professionally oriented context, emphasizing dialogic interaction. Such methods encourage students to think critically, analyze information, consider alternative viewpoints, and engage in discussions – skills essential for addressing complex challenges related to their future professional activities. Various forms of work are utilized to achieve this: individual, paired, and group tasks, along with research projects, role-playing games, document analysis, and engagement with diverse information sources (Barabanova, 2005).

Recently, instructors have been compelled to focus more on grammar when preparing students for exams and tests, which has led to limited opportunities for developing oral communication skills. The global repertoire of foreign language teaching methodologies offers a wide range of interactive methods that, when adapted to a specific curriculum, can be effectively employed in grammar instruction. This approach transforms the perception of grammatical phenomena from being isolated from

the act of communication, making grammar exercises more engaging and less about mechanical manipulation of grammatical forms. Cooperative learning is an instructional approach that involves small group work, creating opportunities for discussing each issue, defending, and justifying one's viewpoint. This method not only fosters a deeper understanding of the subject matter but also enhances thinking and speaking skills. Large groups are divided into smaller ones, each following a set of instructions specially designed by the instructor. Each student works on their specific task, focusing on their portion of the material until they fully understand the studied topic and complete their part. Then, students share their findings, recognizing that each contribution is critical and essential for the work of others, as the absence of any part would result in an incomplete task (some important information would be lost, and other students would not receive it). The method of "cooperative learning" is sometimes translated as "collaborative learning." The key conditions for the effectiveness of cooperative activities include: students understanding their interdependence with other group members and feeling personal responsibility for achieving group goals; engaging in interactions where students help each other learn; and developing the ability to work together and solve potential professional challenges (Barabanova, 2005).

The "brainstorming" method (also known as "brain attack" or "deferred judgment") was proposed by Donald Phillips (USA). It is applied when a group faces the challenge of finding new solutions and approaches to a situation. "Brain attack" significantly enhances the effectiveness of generating new ideas in a large audience (20–30 people). Its main objective is to identify a range of solutions to a single problem within a short time frame. Brainstorming is a technique that stimulates creative activity and productivity for problem-solving. "Brain attack" is a method for addressing urgent tasks within a very limited time. The essence of the method lies in expressing the maximum number of ideas in a short period, followed by discussion and selection of these ideas. This method is used for developing creative abilities or solving complex problems. The brainstorming method can be utilized in various forms of activity: in work with small groups, teams, large groups (such as "audience participation"), and in one-on-one individual work. The use of these methods, especially in small group settings, supports the development of communication skills, collaboration abilities, argumentation, and the capacity to reach compromises. Cooperative learning, in particular, deserves attention, as it involves working in small groups where each participant is responsible for a specific part of a task, fostering collective information processing and achieving shared goals (Dyjakchova, 2014).

Discussion methods are a type of group learning method based on organizational communication in the process of solving educational and professional tasks. Due to its multifunctionality, the discussion method can be considered a universal approach for learning the English language. Additionally, it provides opportunities to search for and reinforce positive models of communicative behavior among students. In this sense, the method can be viewed as a didactic technique in the process of purposefully forming speaking skills in English. The method involves presenting participants with a situation that entails certain psychological relationships, which they are encouraged to consider from the perspective of selecting a specific type of behavior: the most appropriate, the most likely, and the permissible. The method is built on typical examples, teaching students to apply theoretical rules of grammar, pronunciation, and vocabulary in practice while also allowing participants to analyze specific situations and identify errors (Pavlenko, 2014).

Situational modeling methods, such as simulation-based and role-playing games, enable students to acquire procedural competencies and reflect on problem-solving strategies (Diachkova, 2014). This creates conditions for the development of critical thinking, creative engagement, and adaptability – crucial skills for the preparation of specialists in both technical and humanities fields. Such methods also aid students in mastering grammatical content by integrating it into authentic

communicative scenarios, thereby significantly enhancing the quality of teaching English as a professional language. Combinatorial simulation games are employed to develop language culture and assess acquired knowledge. In such games, memory is engaged, making them suitable for the assimilation and reinforcement of material. This represents a reproductive level of thinking, where students perform actions from memory without prompts. Automated skills are better recognized and understood by students, as the means are directly linked to thinking, thereby facilitating the enhancement of their ability to apply knowledge in situations close to real-life contexts. Strategic games are more complex and possess a certain role-based aspect (students' actions are dictated not only by the situation and rules of the game but also by behavioral characteristics imposed by the role and the specifics of the scenario being enacted). This involves a partially exploratory, heuristic level, and sometimes a creative level of thinking. Strategic games are utilized for learning new material and acquiring new experiences under non-standard conditions while also summarizing previously studied content. They foster a deeper connection between students' knowledge and their future professional activities, leading to an understanding of professional issues and possible solutions to them.

It should be noted that the conditions under which the learning process occurs have changed somewhat. Depending on the region and the security situation, higher education seekers and instructors may be located in their permanent residence city, in another region of Ukraine, or outside the country. Furthermore, those studying in unfamiliar regions or abroad may not all have access to computers; thus, they participate in the educational process exclusively via mobile phones. It is essential to remember that an air raid alert signal may sound at any time. In light of this, when organizing classes, it is crucial to consider time zone differences, the possibility of joining online sessions, the availability and quality of internet connectivity, the technical capabilities of participants in the educational process, and other factors. Distance learning during wartime can be conducted in both synchronous and asynchronous modes. However, in our opinion, the best results can be achieved by using hybrid learning, meaning that part of the material is covered in synchronous mode while the remainder is addressed asynchronously. It is necessary to discuss the rules for working in both synchronous and asynchronous modes, as well as the actions to be taken in the event of an air raid alert affecting any participants in the educational process. For the instructor, it is essential to create a favorable and positive atmosphere in the classroom, establish trusting relationships with students, pay attention to the psycho-emotional state of the participants, and provide psychological support when necessary.

In teaching English, a successful combination of communicative and activity-based approaches is essential. It is important to work on the socio-cultural context of the content of knowledge. One cannot ignore the fact that some learners are located outside our country and are gaining knowledge about the cultures of other nations, allowing them to compare various aspects of life with life in Ukraine, form an understanding of living in a globalized world, and compare systems of universal and national values. During practical sessions, a successful approach involves combining traditional teaching methods with innovative ones. For direct meetings with learners, resources such as Zoom, Google Meet, Microsoft Teams, Hangouts, and Skype can be utilized; for assignment posting, knowledge assessment, and testing, platforms like Google Classroom, Edmodo, and Moodle can be employed. Considering that not all learners can attend classes, resources such as YouTube can be used to explain grammatical material, discuss the usage of lexical units, and familiarize students with the realities of English-speaking countries.

Instructors can also create audio-visual materials independently and upload them to accessible platforms for further discussion with learners. Today, foreign language instructors have access to educational services that allow the creation of numerous creative assignments, didactic materials, presentations, quizzes, and test control tasks. Some examples include:

- Edpuzzle: a platform that enables users to create their own videos for explaining new material or project work;
- Kahoot: a platform that allows users to create their own quizzes and interactive tasks;
- Learningapps.org: a platform that hosts a vast number of tasks for practicing and testing grammatical and lexical material, with the option to create custom tasks;
- slides.com: a platform designed for creating presentations and multimedia projects.

In today's environment, learners have access to numerous resources for free informal education, which can help improve their English language proficiency. Among these are: BBC Learning English, British Council Learn English, Busuu, Campster, Coursera, Drops, Duolingo, EnglishDom, Future Learn, Genius Space, Grammar Guru, Lingo Hut, Real English, Tutlo, UTalk, and others (Vasylieva, 2022).

Some participants in the educational process have been forced to relocate within Ukraine or abroad due to threats to life, military actions, and the temporary occupation of certain territories. Many educators and students still remain in temporarily occupied territories and require special support from the state. Some educational institutions have been physically destroyed. Consequently, certain problems arise that require immediate solutions.

This situation has compelled the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine, educational administrators, and civil society to seek urgent solutions on how to organize the educational process for students in their places of permanent residence and evacuation, when to conclude the academic year, how to assess higher education seekers and issue their diplomas, how to ensure the payment of salaries to educational institution staff, and how to provide psychological support, among other concerns. Thus, despite the most challenging times in Ukraine, the educational process in higher educational institutions is being conducted in a distance or blended format, depending on the security situation. For the Ukrainian educational system, this challenge has also become a catalyst for much-needed modernization changes in education, opening a window to new opportunities. This primarily involves the development of digital and distance education, particularly online education. However, the prospects for transforming education are not limited to these areas. The development of informal and non-formal education also requires close attention, as does the creation of mechanisms for recognizing its outcomes within the formal education system. There is a pressing need for testing and widespread implementation of modern teaching methods using information technology (Education in a State of Martial Law, 2022).

Alongside this, a number of problems related to distance learning arise. Firstly, there is a lack of internet access, or participants in the educational process may not be able to connect to the internet. As mentioned above, many people are forced to leave their homes and move to safer locations due to military actions, where internet resources may be unavailable. Secondly, some higher education seekers are unable to study remotely due to their volunteer activities, service in the Armed Forces of Ukraine, involvement in territorial defense units, or work commitments. Thirdly, there are unscrupulous students who take advantage of the difficult situation in Ukraine and skip classes without justification. However, it is impossible to clarify the circumstances under which they miss distance classes. Fourthly, many students are located in territories temporarily occupied by the Russian Federation. Here, numerous questions arise regarding the education of such students and the completion of the academic year or education in general, as well as obtaining diplomas. In this case, it is recommended to utilize available electronic resources, regional platforms, resources of higher education institutions, and so on, in any scenario. Fifthly, unfortunately, not all academic staff are skilled in applying innovative teaching methods, which affects the quality of education for higher education seekers (The Ukrainian Higher Education System in the Context of Russian Military Aggression, 2022). As a result, it is necessary to conduct classes

and workshops aimed at training higher education institutions' academic staff in the application of innovative teaching methods during the distance education process. Thus, despite certain problematic issues related to distance learning, it makes education more accessible. However, in choosing this format, we should not have to choose between accessibility and quality. Higher education should be accessible to all based on each individual's abilities. It should strengthen the skills and abilities of higher education seekers that are necessary for their lives and for understanding others; for conflict resolution; for teamwork and planning common goals and a shared future; for respecting pluralism and diversity (such as gender, ethnic background, religion, and culture); as well as for active participation in societal life. It should also help students master cognitive methods: the basic means of communication and oral speech, literacy, problem formulation and resolution; to gain both general and in-depth knowledge in various fields; to understand rights and responsibilities; and, most importantly, to learn how to learn.

3.2 Swedish practice and context

The newly implemented teaching programme for comprehensive schools reinforces language teaching by making the learning of a second foreign language compulsory, by increasing language class hours and by introducing Spanish on an equal footing with German and French. These measures are in keeping with Sweden's long tradition of language teaching, which has always held a place of honour in the Swedish school curriculum. This article sets out to describe the evolution and organisation of foreign language teaching as well as the status and image related to the languages that are taught. When the Swedish governing coalition government came into office in autumn 1991, one of its spokesmen, the Minister of Education, pointed out the necessity of reinforcing language teaching in the school context. This materialised with the introduction of a new teaching programme in 1994, which made compulsory the learning of a second foreign language. English had already been made compulsory for all pupils in 1962 when the *grundskola* was created to cover nine school years in a unique framework. Language teaching therefore holds a place of honour in the Swedish school curriculum. And one is entitled to wonder if this choice made by the Swedish school authorities is a recent phenomenon (Cabau-Lampa, 1999).

The present-day situation in Sweden in the field of language education with the learning of two compulsory foreign languages brings us back to the time where this dual linguistic training was obligatory for pupils wishing to continue their studies at high school and university. The difference is that this training is not reserved to a minority of privileged pupils anymore. After a presentation of how the Swedish school system has developed throughout the centuries, the article discusses the status and organization of language teaching. It then focuses on the three languages that have traditionally been taught, i.e. German, French and English, before giving an overview of the present-day situation (Cabau-Lam, 2005).

According to the scientific work of Camilla Bardel, before delving into the specifics of foreign language education in Sweden, it's important to first understand the linguistic landscape of the country. In 2009, the Swedish Parliament enacted the Language Act, which designated Swedish as the primary language of the nation. This legislation affirms that Swedish serves as the common language within society, ensuring that all residents are entitled to receive information in Swedish and can expect to communicate in this language across various societal domains. While Sweden has maintained a relatively homogeneous linguistic environment for a considerable time, other languages have coexisted alongside Swedish. For instance, Finland and Sweden were united as one country for 800 years until 1809, during which Finnish emerged as a significant minority language. Since Finland gained independence, there has been a steady influx of Finnish speakers migrating to Sweden. Historically, immigration to Sweden has occurred, albeit in limited numbers, predominantly from neighboring northern European nations. However, since the early

years following World War II, immigration to Sweden has seen a consistent increase. According to recent data, nearly one-fifth of Sweden's population was born abroad, indicating a diverse influx of people from nearly every country worldwide. This broad immigration brings with it a rich tapestry of languages; estimates suggest that around 200 languages are currently spoken in Sweden (Bardel et al., 2023).

Stage model for foreign language instruction and learning

The teaching and learning of foreign languages within the compulsory education system and upper secondary education in Sweden are organized into seven stages, corresponding to the levels outlined in the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR) (Council of Europe, 2001, 2020). This structure is illustrated in Figure 1. The alignment signifies that students are expected to achieve a certain CEFR level as a minimum by the conclusion of each stage of their studies. However, it is important to note that a comprehensive empirical study to validate this alignment has not yet been conducted. For instance, students studying English are expected to attain a CEFR level of B1.2 by the end of English 5 in Year 10, which is the first year of upper secondary school. Stages 1 to 4 are applicable to compulsory education, while Stages 5 to 7 pertain to upper secondary education. Students have the option to select a modern language (ML) in Year 6, aiming to reach Stage 2 by the end of Year 9. They may then progress to Stage 3 during their time in upper secondary school. Additionally, as part of their elective courses, students can choose to learn a second ML, achieving Stage 1 by Year 9 and continuing to Stage 2 in upper secondary school. Furthermore, students may also begin a new ML at Stage 1 in upper secondary school (Skolverket, 2021).

For admission to bachelor's-level courses and programs, the standard entry requirements mandate a minimum of grade E in Swedish (or Swedish as a second language), Mathematics, and English. At the university level, English retains a more significant status compared to other languages, mirroring its prominence in the educational system. A report from a study conducted at Stockholm University by Bolton and Kuteeva (2012) indicated that the prevalence of English usage is notably higher in scientific disciplines than in the humanities and social sciences, where it is generally employed as a supplementary language to Swedish.

A substantial proportion of scientific publications in Sweden is produced in English, reinforcing the language's dominant position within the academic landscape. Two recent doctoral dissertations further elucidate this phenomenon. Salö (2016) demonstrated that the majority of academic texts at the university level are authored in English. While Swedish is employed for scientific purposes to a certain degree—particularly in popular science and some scholarly reports in the humanities—recent years have seen an enhanced emphasis on English due to prevailing research policies in Sweden, which acknowledge its significance in achieving impact on the global research stage.

Moreover, Jämsvi's (2020) investigation into the evolution of language policies governing higher education institutions from the 1970s to the present revealed a transformation in the perception and valuation of multilingualism in Sweden. During the 1970s, there was a clear ambition to embrace multilingualism as relevant and advantageous for higher education. The 1974 internationalization study presented to the Swedish Government advocated for the necessity of Swedes to acquire proficiency in several global languages, including Chinese, French, German, and Russian. In contrast, this perspective appears to have diminished in the twenty-first century. Jämsvi's analysis found that contemporary policy documents reflect a prevailing notion equating English with internationalization. This ideological shift signifies a transition away from solidarity as a core value, giving way to the influence of market forces and economic interests across various societal domains, which consequently enhances the status of English.

Trends in foreign language studies in higher education

In recent years, Sweden has witnessed a notable decline in interest toward the study of foreign languages at the university level. In 2016, the Association of Swedish Higher Education Institutions (SUHF) established a working group to assess the status of language programs within higher education and to propose future initiatives (SUHF, 2017). The resulting report underscored the necessity for a national language strategy that delineates the direction for specific initiatives and tasks that need to be undertaken. It also highlighted the extent to which foreign language programs have been discontinued across universities between 2008 and 2016. For instance, French has been eliminated from six universities, English from five, Russian from four, while Finnish, German, Greek, Italian, and Spanish have been cut from three universities, among other examples.

In transitioning from the previous discourse on language learning to the current focus on language teaching, it is important to highlight the findings of Bardel et al. (2023) regarding terminological issues in language education research. An edited volume from Umeå University, authored by Lindgren and Enever, addresses a range of topics pertinent to language education, primarily exploring the gap between research and practice in this domain. The Swedish term "språkdidaktik" often encapsulates this field, particularly in conjunction with teacher education in Sweden, and it represents an expanding area of research. According to the editors, "språkdidaktik" encompasses both the subject matter of language and the theories and practices of teaching and learning. They further note that the Swedish term "didaktik" and the German "Didaktik" is broader than the English term "didactics," which typically focuses primarily on teaching methodologies.

However, the intricate relationship among the terms 'didactics,' 'teaching and learning,' and 'language education' requires further elucidation. Language education encompasses various aspects pertinent to teaching and learning, including the role of language development in subjects beyond language itself. Some contributions within Lindgren and Enever's volume touch upon this complexity, examining diverse subfields of language education.

The studies presented in this volume reflect prominent topics in Swedish research, such as grammar instruction, collaborative learning in university-level language courses, and the use of Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL). These themes resonate with ongoing discussions related to formal linguistic structures, the intersection of language teaching and information and communication technology (ICT), language policy, multilingualism, and Content and Language Integrated Learning (CLIL).

In the area of vocabulary, phraseology, and grammar in language education, research on teaching materials remains sparse but is recognized as significant. Two studies focusing on vocabulary in English textbooks for young learners and one examining grammar in Italian textbooks shed light on this topic. The literature on vocabulary acquisition emphasizes the necessity of multiple exposures to lexical items and phrases. Studies analyzing vocabulary in textbooks for young learners reveal a lack of conscious rationale in vocabulary selection, highlighting the need for alignment with research findings. Shifting focus from teaching materials to teaching interventions and teacher beliefs, research indicates that English teachers can enhance students' collocational skills through minor adjustments in instructional strategies. Additionally, interviews with EFL teachers demonstrate their awareness of vocabulary's role in language acquisition, although vocabulary instruction is not often prioritized as an independent learning objective. The integration of ICT in language education is crucial, given its widespread implementation in Swedish education. However, few studies on Computer Assisted Language Learning have emerged recently. Research highlights the potential of web-based technologies for fostering linguistic and cultural competencies in students. Studies on text-based interaction and students' use of online resources underscore the need for increased awareness of

diverse writing genres and enhanced technological competencies within foreign language education. Overall, the findings of Bardel, Gyllstad, and Tholin contribute valuable insights into the evolving landscape of language education research, emphasizing the importance of bridging theory and practice in this dynamic field (Bardel et al., 2023).

4 Discussions

The teaching of foreign languages, particularly English, is evolving in both Ukraine and Sweden, each adapting to their unique socio-cultural and educational contexts. While both countries recognize the importance of interactive methods in language education, their approaches differ significantly due to varying pedagogical traditions and current challenges. In Ukraine, contemporary higher education institutions increasingly utilize interactive methods and technologies to teach English as a professional language. These approaches are designed to enhance student motivation, align with their interests, and facilitate the integration of new knowledge with prior experiences. The emphasis on active involvement in the learning process enables students to manage their own educational progress (Barabanova, 2005; Dyiakchova, 2014). The interactive methods employed, such as cooperative learning and brainstorming, not only enhance grammatical skills but also encourage critical thinking and problem-solving. For example, cooperative learning, which divides larger groups into smaller ones, fosters collaboration and interdependence among students, making each member's contribution essential for group success (Barabanova, 2005).

Despite the positive aspects of these methods, the Ukrainian educational landscape faces challenges due to the ongoing conflict and the need for distance learning. Many students are displaced, with varying access to technology and the internet, necessitating a blend of synchronous and asynchronous learning to accommodate different needs. This situation has prompted educators to adopt innovative tools like Google Classroom and Zoom while creating engaging multimedia resources for students. However, issues such as internet access and varying levels of technological proficiency among academic staff present obstacles to effective implementation (Education in a State of Martial Law, 2022).

Moreover, Ukrainian educators are urged to combine communicative and activity-based approaches, focusing on the socio-cultural context of the content. The significance of fostering an understanding of global and national values among students is crucial, especially for those learning in a foreign context (Vasylieva, 2022). Despite these challenges, the need for educational reform during these trying times has catalyzed the integration of digital technologies and innovative teaching methods in Ukrainian higher education.

In Sweden, foreign language education, particularly English, is characterized by a strong emphasis on communicative competence and a student-centered approach. Swedish pedagogical practices often prioritize collaboration, critical thinking, and real-world application of language skills. The use of project-based learning and authentic assessments allows students to engage meaningfully with the language and develop their linguistic abilities in contexts that mirror real-life situations (Woods, 2014).

Swedish educators also leverage technology in language teaching, utilizing platforms like Google Classroom and various

online resources to enhance learning. The Swedish educational framework encourages flexibility, allowing educators to tailor their teaching methods to meet the diverse needs of their students. This adaptability is particularly relevant in today's globalized world, where students are often exposed to different cultures and languages, fostering a broader understanding of communication in diverse contexts.

4.1 Comparative analysis of two practice of foreign language teaching in Ukraine and Sweden

While both Ukrainian and Swedish practices in foreign language teaching emphasize interactive and student-centered approaches, the context in which these practices are applied differs significantly. In Ukraine, the ongoing conflict necessitates a focus on innovative teaching methods that can be delivered through distance learning, often under challenging circumstances. In contrast, Sweden's well-established educational infrastructure allows for a more integrated approach to language learning, emphasizing collaboration and real-world applications without the immediate pressures of a crisis.

In Sweden, the language instruction framework is aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), categorizing foreign language learning into seven stages, reflecting systematic progression from basic to advanced proficiency (Skolverket, 2021). This alignment emphasizes a clear set of expectations regarding language competency, with students expected to achieve certain CEFR levels at various educational stages. English, being a dominant language in academia and the workplace, is taught extensively, reinforcing its significance in the curriculum (Bolton & Kuteeva, 2012).

In Ukraine, the foreign language curriculum, particularly English, is increasingly focused on developing practical communication skills. The challenges posed by the war necessitate innovative pedagogical approaches, including the integration of interactive methods and technologies (user's preferences). Current practices in Ukrainian higher education emphasize a shift from traditional rote learning to more communicative and task-based methodologies, aiming to foster critical thinking and real-world language use.

4.2 Integration of technology and teaching methodologies

Swedish language education embraces modern methodologies, incorporating digital tools and resources to enhance learning experiences. The integration of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) has been pivotal in facilitating language acquisition, with a focus on collaborative learning and learner autonomy (Bardel et al., 2023). Despite the general success in integrating ICT, there remains a call for further research on its effectiveness, especially concerning vocabulary and grammar instruction. In Ukraine, the shift towards interactive and technology-driven methodologies is becoming increasingly pronounced, particularly in response to the needs of students affected by the war. The use of digital platforms for language learning has surged, aiming to maintain educational continuity amidst disruptions (user's project details). However, there are concerns regarding the adequacy of teacher training in utilizing these technologies effectively, which parallels challenges observed in Sweden.

Here's a comparative Table 1 summarizing the practices of foreign language teaching in Ukraine and Sweden based on the information provided.

Table 1: the practices of foreign language teaching in Ukraine and Sweden

Aspect	Ukraine	Sweden
Historical Context	Rapid reforms in response to the ongoing war with Russia.	Longstanding emphasis on foreign language education since 1962.
Policy Framework	National policies aim to enhance English proficiency for European integration.	Language Act (2009) designates Swedish as the primary language; English is dominant.
Compulsory Languages	English is the primary focus, with increasing emphasis on European languages.	Two foreign languages are compulsory; Spanish introduced alongside German and French.
Teaching Methodologies	Shift from rote learning to communicative and task-based approaches, influenced by war conditions.	Structured alignment with the CEFR, emphasizing progression through seven stages.

Integration of Technology	Growing use of digital platforms and interactive methods in response to war disruptions.	Incorporation of ICT in teaching; focus on collaborative learning and learner autonomy.
Current Challenges	Disruption of educational continuity due to war; need for practical language use.	Declining interest in foreign language studies at the university level; need for revitalization strategies.
Opportunities for Improvement	Collaboration with international partners for best practices in language pedagogy.	National strategy needed to address declining language program interest and maintain relevance.
Teacher Training	Urgent need for enhanced training on the use of technology and innovative methodologies.	Ongoing emphasis on teacher education, although challenges remain in implementing effective ICT strategies.
Cultural and Linguistic Diversity	Increasing multilingualism due to immigration; emphasis on practical language skills.	Diverse linguistic landscape; approximately 200 languages spoken due to immigration.
Status of English	English is gaining prominence, especially in higher education and professional contexts.	English is dominant in academia; substantial scientific publications are produced in English.

This comparative analysis examines foreign language education practices in Ukraine and Sweden, highlighting distinct approaches shaped by their historical and socio-political contexts. Ukraine's educational framework is undergoing rapid reforms in response to the ongoing conflict with Russia, necessitating a reactive approach to language education focused primarily on enhancing English proficiency for European integration. In contrast, Sweden boasts a stable historical commitment to foreign language education, emphasized since 1962, promoting a bilingual policy that values both Swedish and English. In terms of compulsory languages, Ukraine prioritizes English while Sweden mandates the study of two foreign languages, fostering broader linguistic competencies. Methodologically, Ukraine is shifting towards communicative and task-based approaches, responding to immediate needs, whereas Sweden employs structured methodologies aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR), supporting systematic skill development.

Technology integration is on the rise in Ukraine, driven by wartime disruptions, while Sweden has established frameworks for incorporating Information and Communication Technology (ICT) in education, focusing on collaborative learning. Current challenges differ: Ukraine faces educational disruptions and the need for practical language skills, while Sweden grapples with declining interest in foreign language studies at the university level. Opportunities for improvement include Ukraine's potential collaboration with international partners for best practices in language pedagogy, and Sweden's need for a national strategy to rejuvenate language programs. Teacher training remains urgent in Ukraine to equip educators with innovative methodologies, while Sweden continues to emphasize ongoing professional development, particularly in ICT implementation. Finally, both countries are experiencing increasing cultural and linguistic diversity, necessitating tailored approaches to language education, with English's status growing in Ukraine and already dominant in Sweden's academic landscape.

5. Conclusions

Both Ukraine and Sweden have rich histories of foreign language teaching, but the current context significantly shapes their approaches. Ukraine's language education is heavily influenced by ongoing conflict, prompting a shift towards practical language skills for integration into European systems. In contrast, Sweden has a long-standing tradition of foreign language education, emphasizing multilingualism as a core value.

Policy Frameworks: Ukrainian policies are focused on enhancing English proficiency as part of a broader strategy for European integration, responding to urgent needs created by the war. Conversely, Sweden's policies reflect a well-established framework that prioritizes the learning of multiple foreign languages within its education system. **Teaching Methodologies and Integration of Technology:** Ukraine is moving away from rote learning to more communicative and task-based approaches, particularly in the context of digital learning due to war-induced disruptions. Sweden, however, maintains a structured approach aligned with the Common European Framework of Reference for Languages (CEFR), integrating ICT into language instruction, but may need to adapt to changing student interests.

Challenges and Opportunities. Ukraine faces significant challenges in maintaining educational continuity due to the war, while Sweden is experiencing a decline in interest in foreign language studies at the university level. Both countries have opportunities to collaborate internationally, share best practices, and innovate in language pedagogy. **Cultural and Linguistic Diversity:** Ukraine's increasing multilingualism due to immigration presents a challenge and an opportunity for language teaching, focusing on practical language skills. In Sweden, the coexistence of numerous languages enriches the educational landscape but also requires a nuanced approach to language instruction. **Recommendations** **Enhancing Teacher Training:** Ukraine should prioritize training for language teachers in innovative methodologies and the use of digital platforms to adapt to the ongoing challenges of wartime education. Sweden could benefit from continual professional development that addresses current trends in language teaching and integrates modern technologies effectively.

Refreshing Foreign Language Programs. Sweden should develop a national language strategy that outlines initiatives to rekindle interest in foreign language studies at the university level. This might include increased funding for language programs, awareness campaigns, and integration of language learning with career readiness. **Promoting Practical Language Use:** In both countries, language curricula should emphasize practical language use in real-life contexts. This can be achieved through project-based learning, exchanges, and collaborations with international partners, especially for Ukrainian institutions seeking to enhance English proficiency. **Leveraging Technology:** Both Ukraine and Sweden should continue to harness the potential of technology in language teaching. This includes the development of online platforms that facilitate collaborative learning and provide access to diverse language resources, thereby enhancing engagement and improving learning outcomes. **Fostering Multilingualism:** Both countries should actively promote multilingualism as a valuable skill. Ukraine can create language programs that include minority languages and languages of significant immigrant populations. Sweden could continue to support initiatives that embrace the country's diverse linguistic landscape, preparing students for global citizenship.

Research and Evaluation. Establishing a robust research framework in both countries to evaluate foreign language teaching practices and their effectiveness is essential. This should include comprehensive studies on the alignment of curricula with the CEFR, as well as assessments of student outcomes and engagement. By addressing these conclusions and implementing the recommendations, both Ukraine and Sweden can enhance their foreign language teaching practices, ensuring that students are well-equipped for a globalized world.

Further investigations of the topic regarding foreign language education practices in Ukraine and Sweden could encompass a range of areas to deepen understanding and inform future developments: investigate the effectiveness of recent educational reforms in Ukraine, particularly regarding language education, and analyze the adaptability of teaching strategies in response to wartime challenges, task-based approaches in Ukraine compare with Sweden's CEFR-aligned methodologies in terms of student outcomes, digital tools are being implemented in classrooms and

their impact on language learning outcomes, along with teacher training programs that support technology use etc.

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